

Family support, need for achievement, and entrepreneurial orientation on entrepreneurial intentions in vulnerable groups

Fatwa Tentama¹, Surahma Asti Mulasari², Tri Wahyuni Sukesi², Sulistyawati², Subardjo³

¹Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

²Faculty of Public Health, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

³Faculty of Law, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to design and test the goodness of fit of a theoretical model that describes the effect of family support, need for achievement, and entrepreneurial orientation on entrepreneurial intentions with empirical data in the field. Research participation used subjects totaling 66 people from Ngalang village who were female, did not have permanent jobs, and were included in the poor category. Data collection uses four measurement scales: the entrepreneurial intention scale, family support scale, need for achievement scale, and entrepreneurial orientation scale, and is analyzed using partial least square (PLS) via smartPLS 3.0. The results of the study show the formation of a theoretical model of the influence of family support, need for achievement, and entrepreneurial orientation on entrepreneurial intentions that fit with empirical data. Family support has a positive and very significant effect on entrepreneurial intentions, the need for achievement does not affect an entrepreneurial orientation, and entrepreneurial orientation has a positive and very significant impact on entrepreneurial intentions. This research implies that this model can be used as a reference and applied to overcoming economic problems in vulnerable groups.

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Corresponding Author:

Fatwa Tentama
Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan
Kapas Street, No. 9, Semaki, Umbulharjo, Yogyakarta
Email: fatwa.tentama@psy.uad.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia has impacted all fields or aspects of human life, such as health, education, economy, employment, entrepreneurship, and others. Even though the current normal or post-pandemic situation remains worrisome and affects the community, especially in the entrepreneurship or business sector and occupation, many people have lost their jobs as employees or entrepreneurs. Many agencies, companies, or factories carry out termination of employment, and many entrepreneurs closed their businesses or went bankrupt due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Based on the Central Bureau of Statistics, in 2022 [1], there will be 144.01 million people in the workforce, but the working population will be 135.61 million. There are 11.53 million people (5.83%) with an open unemployment rate, with the detail that 0.96 million people are unemployed because of COVID-19, as many as 0.55 million people are not in the labor force because of COVID-19, as many as 0.58 million people are out of work as civilians due to COVID-19. As many as 9.44 million people got reduced working hours due to COVID-19.

Employees who get laid off or are unemployed will look for ways to keep working, and one of them is by establishing entrepreneurship [2]. Entrepreneurship is one of the main drivers of economic development,

recognized by researchers and practitioners [3]. Entrepreneurs who went bankrupt or closed down their businesses also need a strong will to continue their business again. Entrepreneurial intention is essential in overcoming these problems because it determines whether they continue to work in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial intention can represent an individual's commitment when starting a business [4].

The entrepreneurial intention concept views entrepreneurial intention as an instinct and willingness to become an entrepreneur [5]. Entrepreneurial intention plays a vital role in the initial stage of a business [6]. Entrepreneurial intention is an individual's belief in establishing a new business and consciously planning to develop it to some point in the future [7]. According to Gelderen *et al.* [8], entrepreneurial intentions consist of four dimensions. They are i) desires are the interest and intention to start a business, ii) preferences indicate that entrepreneurship is a requirement that one must achieve; and iii) plans are the expectations that exist within the individual when starting a business in the future; iv) behavior expectancies are the possibility of entrepreneurship with the target of starting a business.

Entrepreneurial intention is critical in this COVID-19 pandemic era. Individuals with entrepreneurial intentions will bring up the will to create a new business by looking at existing business opportunities [9]. In addition, entrepreneurial intentions display positive attitudes and behavior when facing risks that might arise [10] and can think and create new businesses [11]. However, individuals with low entrepreneurial intentions tend to negatively perceive the numerous risks arising from entrepreneurship negatively [12] and feel confused when entrepreneurial opportunities come [13]. Furthermore, they quickly give up when encountering obstacles in entrepreneurship, as explained by Alamari, Newbery, Haddoud, and Beaumont [14], and the difficulty of creating jobs [15].

Many factors influence the emergence of entrepreneurial intentions, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. According to Ajzen [16], three factors affect entrepreneurial intentions i.e., i) Social factors are the factors that influence entrepreneurial intentions coming from outside the individual. ii) Personal factors are the factors that influence entrepreneurial intentions coming from within the Individual; such factors include emotions, attitudes, personality, values, and intelligence. Lastly, iii) information factors are personal knowledge of an object derived from numerous sources, including experience and expertise. In several previous studies, Ibrahim and Lucky; Martins and Perez; Singh and Mehdi [17]-[19] reveal that entrepreneurial orientation is an internal factor influencing the formation of entrepreneurial intention, need for achievement, in the study by [20]-[22], external factors include family support [23]-[25].

Entrepreneurial orientation is one of the internal factors that influence entrepreneurial intentions in individuals. Entrepreneurial orientation is the most critical factor in innovation or business [26]. Entrepreneurial orientation is also referred to as individuals who can see an opportunity through the entrepreneurship concept and the actions taken [27]. Individuals with an entrepreneurial orientation tend to accept innovative business processes, practices, and decision-making, are willing to take risks and are proactive [28]. Previous research has revealed that there is a relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and entrepreneurial intentions in individuals [17]-[19]. Aspects of entrepreneurial orientation refer to Covin and Selvin's theory [27] which consists of three dimensions, innovation, risk-taking, and proactiveness.

The other internal factors that influence entrepreneurial intentions are the need for achievement. The need for achievement is an impulse arising within individuals so that they can face problems and become successful individuals [29]. Individuals who need achievement tend to have the drive to achieve high standards and a business that is going well [30]. Individuals who need achievement will be motivated to carry out their tasks effectively [31]. Several previous studies have discovered that there is a relationship between the need for achievement and entrepreneurial intentions [20]-[22]. Aspects of the need for achievement refer to McClelland's theory [29]; they are innovative and creative, responsible, feedback, persistent, and challenging tasks.

In addition to the need for achievement, family support also influences entrepreneurial intentions. Family support is the family attitude toward accepting family members [32]. Family support is a resource that can protect individual entrepreneurial intentions [33]. Families can provide instrumental and affective support to individuals, and then this support will increase feelings and intentions to open a business [34]. Several previous studies have revealed that there is a relationship between family support and entrepreneurial intentions [23]-[25]. Aspects of family support refer to Sarafino and Smith's theory [35]. They are emotional support, reward support, instrumental support, and informative support.

Based on the explanation above, there is a relationship between entrepreneurial orientation, the need for achievement, and family support towards entrepreneurial intentions which can be shown in Figure 1.

Research on entrepreneurial intentions in society during the COVID-19 pandemic was still small and relatively new, especially regarding the development of models of entrepreneurial intentions in communities during the COVID-19 pandemic. This problem is more specific to women's society. Women in Ngalang Village can become independent entrepreneurs when they get laid off; most do not have permanent jobs and do not have businesses. There are many business opportunities for women in Ngalang Village by utilizing the potential available in nature at Ngalang Village. This study aims to design and develop a model

of entrepreneurial intention and its influencing factors that will be tested in the relevant environment to determine whether the model fits with empirical data in the field.

Figure 1. Intervariable relationship

2. METHOD

2.1. Participant

Participants in this study were residents of Ngalang Village, Gedangsari, Gunungkidul, Yogyakarta, who are female, do not have permanent jobs, and are categorized as poor. The participants in this study were 66 women, if the population is small, the researchers account for all samples as the population [36].

2.2. Research procedure

The first procedure carried out in this study was to carry out a permit process through the village head to conduct research in Ngalang Village, Gedangsari, Gunungkidul, Yogyakarta. After obtaining research permission from the local village head, the researchers conducted interviews and preliminary observations as a preliminary study in this study. Participants were required to complete and sign an informed consent as proof of their availability to participate in the research without coercion. Participants also have the right to terminate their participation if something disturbing or harms them individually. This process takes place offline from September to October 2021.

2.3. Research instrument

This study uses a Likert scaling model with four choices or alternative answers (responses) to obtain empirical data regarding entrepreneurial intentions, entrepreneurial orientation, need for achievement, and family support. The Entrepreneurial Intention Scale is adopted by researchers based on the previous scale. The entrepreneurial Orientation Scale, Need For Achievement Scale, and Family Support Scale are compiled by researchers based on reference theory. The scale is presented in two types of statements, favorable and unfavorable, with four alternative answer choices ("highly concordant," "concordant," "nonconcordant," and "highly nonconcordant").

The researchers adopted the Entrepreneurial Intention Scale compiled by Tentama and Abdussalam [37], referring to aspects of entrepreneurial intentions according to Gelderen, Brand, Praag, Bodewes, Poutsma, and Gils [8], i.e., desires, preferences, plans, and behavior expectancies. Aspects of desires are reflected in the item "I like things related to the business." The preferences aspect is reflected in items like "I feel ready for entrepreneurship." The plans aspect is reflected in the item "I have plans to start a business after graduation." Behavior expectancies are reflected in the item "I will open a business corresponding to market demand."

Researchers compiled their own entrepreneurial orientation scale referring to entrepreneurial orientation aspects by Covin and Selvin [27], such as innovation, risk-taking, and proactiveness. The innovation aspect is reflected in the item "I prefer to do tasks in my creative way rather than using the old method that other people use." The risk-taking aspect is reflected by the item "I usually act to anticipate future problems, needs or changes." The proactiveness aspect is reflected in the "I still dare to be responsible in an activity even though I doubt my ability."

Furthermore, researchers also compiled a need for achievement scale referring to aspects of the need for achievement by McClelland [29], i.e., innovation and creativity, responsibility, feedback, persistence, and challenging tasks. The innovative and creative aspects are reflected through the item "I like tasks that demand other ways to avoid routine tasks." The element of responsibility is reflected in the item "I complete every task properly and maximally." The feedback aspect is reflected in the "Other people's praise makes me passionate about

achieving achievements." The persistence aspect is reflected in the "I make long-term plans to achieve my goals according to my expertise." The challenging task aspect reflects "I am proud of the best achievement I got."

Researchers compiled the family support scale referring to aspects of family support by Sarafino and Smith [35]: emotional support, appreciation support, instrumental support, and informative support. The emotional support aspect is reflected in the item "The attention from my family makes me happy." The element of reward support is reflected in the item "My family supports my ideas about entrepreneurship." The aspect of instrumental support is reflected in the item "My family provides the capital I need for entrepreneurship." The informative support aspect is reflected in the item "Families are willing to provide information about entrepreneurship."

2.4. Data analysis

The research result is divided into outer and inner test model evaluation. The outer model test aims to test the measurement model that tests convergent validity and discriminant validity. The inner model test seeks to test the structural model of the relationship between exogenous variables and endogenous variables. Structural Equation Model based on partial least square (PLS) used SmartPLS 3.0 software.

3. RESULT

3.1 Outer model test

Measurement model in SmartPLS 3.0 called the outer model. The outer model test aims to specify the relationship between latent variables and their indicators. The outer model analysis consists of convergent validity, discriminant validity, composite reliability, and Cronbach alpha. Tests from the outer model are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Overall model algorithm PLS output

3.1.1. Convergent validity

Convergent validity can be seen from the loading factor value for each indicator (item) and the average variance extracted (AVE) value. A scale is said to meet convergent validity if the loading factor value for each item is >0.5 and the AVE value for each variable is >0.5 [38]. The following is the overall PLS outer model algorithm output.

Based on Table 1, the results of the convergent validity test showed that the factor loadings for each item had met the criteria of >0.5 , which means that all items are valid. The entrepreneurial intention scale consists of 32 items, and 23 of them were valid. The family support scale consists of 24 items, and 18 items were found to be valid. The need for achievement scale consists of 20 items, and 8 items were found to be valid. The entrepreneurial orientation scale consists of 24 items, and 4 items were found to be valid.

Table 1. Item loading factor value in convergent validity test

Variable	Item	Loading factor value	Remark	
Entrepreneurial intention	DS1	0.592	Valid	
	DS13	0.776	Valid	
	DS17	0.723	Valid	
	DS21	0.616	Valid	
	DS25	0.869	Valid	
	DS29	0.556	Valid	
	DS9	0.789	Valid	
	PF10	0.757	Valid	
	PF18	0.746	Valid	
	PF2	0.731	Valid	
	PF22	0.689	Valid	
	PF26	0.576	Valid	
	PF30	0.500	Valid	
	PL11	0.823	Valid	
	PL19	0.882	Valid	
	PL23	0.628	Valid	
	PL27	0.835	Valid	
	PL3	0.907	Valid	
	BE12	0.909	Valid	
	BE20	0.849	Valid	
	BE24	0.540	Valid	
	BE28	0.841	Valid	
	BE4	0.846	Valid	
	Family support	DE13	0.655	Valid
		DE17	0.774	Valid
		DE21	0.672	Valid
		DE9	0.763	Valid
		DIF12	0.833	Valid
		DIF16	0.573	Valid
		DIF20	0.709	Valid
		DIF4	0.825	Valid
		DIF8	0.628	Valid
DIN11		0.860	Valid	
DIN19		0.791	Valid	
DIN23		0.669	Valid	
DIN7		0.665	Valid	
DP10		0.608	Valid	
DP14		0.682	Valid	
DP18		0.682	Valid	
DP2	0.774	Valid		
DP22	0.557	Valid		
Need for achievement	IK16	0.560	Valid	
	MTS15	0.805	Valid	
	MTS5	0.565	Valid	
	PE14	0.876	Valid	
	PE4	0.886	Valid	
	PE9	0.554	Valid	
	TJP13	0.601	Valid	
	TJP3	0.794	Valid	
Entrepreneurial orientation	INS10	0.830	Valid	
	INS3	0.831	Valid	
	PCS18	0.630	Valid	
	PCS21	0.796	Valid	

Table 2. AVE value

Variable	AVE	Remark
Entrepreneurial intention	0.501	Valid
Family support	0.507	Valid
Need for achievement	0.516	Valid
Entrepreneurial orientation	0.602	Valid

Based on Table 2, regarding these variables, entrepreneurial intention, family support, need for achievement, and entrepreneurial orientation, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value meets the > 0.5 criteria, so each variable is valid. So it can be concluded that all research variables have met the requirements of convergent validity. The AVE value > 0.5 means that the latent variable can explain more than 50 percent of the item variance [39].

3.1.2 Discriminant validity

The study carried out discriminant validity tests to ensure that each concept in each latent variable is different from other variables [38]. Discriminant validity can be seen by comparing the AVE root values between variables. The discriminant validity test for each latent variable is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. AVE root values

	Entrepreneurial intention	Family support	Need for achievement	Entrepreneurial orientation
Entrepreneurial intention	0.708			
Family support	0.678	0.712		
Need for achievement	0.560	0.672	0.718	
Entrepreneurial orientation	0.506	0.345	0.591	0.776

Based on the data in Table 3, it is known that the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) root correlation value for each variable is higher than the root correlation value of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) with other variables. So, it can be concluded that all variables in this study have met the requirements of discriminant validity.

3.1.3 Reliability

Hair *et al.* [40] Explained that the reliability value for each variable met the criteria, composite reliability > 0.7 , and Cronbach alpha value > 0.5 . The results of Table 4 imply that entrepreneurial intention, family support, need for achievement, and entrepreneurial orientation variables have a composite reliability value of > 0.7 and Cronbach alpha > 0.7 , so all variables are declared to have good reliability. Testing the validity and reliability shows that all conditions can be met; therefore, it can be continued to test the inner model.

Table 4. Reliability value

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite reliability	Remark
Entrepreneurial intention	0.951	0.957	Reliable
Family support	0.944	0.948	Reliable
Need for achievement	0.860	0.891	Reliable
Entrepreneurial orientation	0.774	0.857	Reliable

3.2 Inner model

This study tested the structural model with the inner model, aiming to ensure that the structural model that has been built is robust and accurate. Evaluation of the inner model includes coefficient of determination (R^2), predictive relevance (Q^2) and goodness of fit index (GoF). Testing is carried out systematically and the results of the inner model evaluation are explained as follows.

3.2.1 Coefficient of determination (R^2)

The coefficient of determination is used to measure the value of endogenous variables that can be explained by exogenous variables or the predictive power of structural models [38]. The R-Square value is divided into several categories, e.g., 0.67 (strong), 0.33 (moderate), and 0.19 (weak) [38]. Based on the results of the analysis shown in Table 5, it shows that the R-square model value is 0.544.

3.2.2 Predictive relevance (Q²)

Evaluation of the results of the structural model can also be done by calculating the predictive relevance of Q² or often called predictive sample reuse. This approach was adapted to PLS using a blindfolding procedure [38]. Q² value>0 indicates that the model has good predictive relevance. Q²<0 implies the model lacks predictive relevance. The predictive relevance value in this study is 0.229. Based on the analysis results, it is known that Q²>0, precisely 0.229, so it is known that the observed values and parameter estimates are produced by models that have good predictive relevance so that they can predict the effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables.

3.2.3 Goodness of fit index (GoF)

The goodness of fit is an index that describes the level of suitability of the overall model, validating the model as a whole such as evaluating measurement models and structural models and carrying out simple measurements for the overall model predictions. The goodness of fit index (GoF) value is between 0 to 1; the interpretation is that a 0.10 value includes a weak GoF level, a 0.25 moderate GoF value, and a 0.36 strong GoF value [38]. For measuring the goodness of fit, the formula is as follows:

$$GoF = \sqrt{Com. R^2}$$

Note:

GoF : *GoF index*

Com : *Average communality index*

R² : *Average R-square*

Table 5. R-square, AVE, and communalities values

Variable	R-square	AVE
Entrepreneurial intention		0.501
Family support		0.507
Need for achievement	0.544	0.516
Entrepreneurial orientation		0.602
Communalities		0.531

$$GoF = \sqrt{0.531 \times 0.544}$$

$$GoF = 0.537$$

Based on the calculation of the GoF formula above, it is known that the resulting GoF is 0.537 > 0.36, so it is included in the strong GoF category [41]. Based on the inner model test, it is known that the proposed reflective model fits according to empirical data in the field. The evaluation results on the inner model can be explained in full in the following Table 6.

Table 6. Results of evaluation of the structural model (inner model)

Indicator	Rule of thumb	Result	Remark
Coefficient of determination (R ²)	0.67 (strong), 0.33 (moderate) and 0.19 (weak)	0.544	The effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables is moderate
Predictive relevance (Q ²)	Q ² >0, Predictive relevance good Q ² <0, Predictive relevance is deficient	0.229	Predictive relevance is good
The goodness of fit (GoF)	Criteria from GoF; 0.1 (weak GoF), 0.25 (moderate GoF), and 0.36 (strong GoF)	0.537	Strong model fit

The Table 6 above implies that the R-square value in this study is 0.544, which means that the effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables is moderate or fair. Evaluation of predictive relevance results using blindfolding shows a good category so that the model can predict the effect of exogenous variables on its endogenous variables. The goodness of fit is an index describing the suitability of the overall model, validating the model as a whole such as evaluating measurement models and structural models and carrying out simple measurements for the overall model predictions. The GoF results show that the model is in a strong category [40]. Based on the inner model test, it is known that the proposed reflective model (fit) corresponds to the empirical data.

3.3 Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing is conducted by looking at the t-statistic value with alpha 5%, the t-statistic >1.96, and the probability value: the p-value <0.05. Then it shows that the hypothesis is accepted, then looking at the original sample value, if the value is (+), it shows a positive effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. At the same time, the value (-) indicates a negative impact of exogenous variables on endogenous variables [37]. Table 7 shows the p-value, t-statistic, and the original sample obtained in this study. Based on the hypothesis testing in the table above, the results can be presented as follows.

Table 7. Hypothesis test results

Variable Influence	Original sample	t-statistic	p-value	Criteria	Remark
Family support>entrepreneurial intention	0.582	5.256	0.000	p<0.01	Positive influence and very significant
Need for achievement>entrepreneurial intention	-0.018	0.109	0.914	p>0.05	No influence
Entrepreneurial orientation>entrepreneurial intention	0.316	2.759	0.000	p<0.06	Positive influence and very significant

4. DISCUSSION

The study results imply that the theoretical model that describes the effect of family support need for achievement and entrepreneurial orientation on entrepreneurial intentions fits with empirical data. This theoretical model is a novelty, testing the model in research on entrepreneurial intentions by involving the interrelationship of several variables, family support, need for achievement, and entrepreneurial orientation that has not been found before. Previous research stated that the entrepreneurial intention model is influenced by entrepreneurship education, family environment, and attitude toward entrepreneurship through self-efficacy [42]. The entrepreneurial intention model is designed to involve self-efficacy and family support [43]. According to Gelderen *et al.* [8], individuals may have entrepreneurial intentions if they have three dimensions of desires (desire to start a business), preferences (decide to choose entrepreneurship), plans (have plans and hopes for the future), and behavior expectancies (having targets as a reference in entrepreneurship).

The second hypothesis test shows that family support positively and very significantly influences entrepreneurial intentions in the community. Families providing much information about entrepreneurship will enlarge a person's intention to become an entrepreneur [44]. The importance of family support to raise intentions in entrepreneurship gives tremendous confidence to individuals that they can increase their potential in entrepreneurship [45]. Research further confirms that the role of family support is to provide emotional support and information that helps a person raise entrepreneurship [46]. As described by Sher, Adil, Mushtaq, Ali, and Hussain [47], family support will help individuals find good ideas and make the right choices in preparing to build their businesses [48]. Family support has a positive effect on entrepreneurial intentions; support provided by family members will impact the propensity to start a business in the future [49]. Starting from the family environment and family support, a person will feel more confident and energetic in pursuing his goals in entrepreneurship. The results of the above research are also reinforced by the study of Annisa, Tentama, and Bashori [50], which states that family support contributes to increasing entrepreneurial intentions marked by emotional support and respect for the business intentions of family members. Family support is translated by providing much information about entrepreneurship to enlarge a person's high intention to run a business [51]. The higher the family support, the higher the people's passion for having entrepreneurial intentions. Individuals who receive family support, such as positive reviews on their ideas, will be more interested and willing to start a business [48], [51].

The third hypothesis test shows no influence between the need for achievement and social entrepreneurial intentions. This result contradicts previous research from Vemmy [52], which discovered that the need for achievement variable positively and significantly affects entrepreneurial intentions. Another study by Nizma and Siregar [53] also indicates that the need for achievement is an influential factor in entrepreneurial intention behavior. Research by [21], [54] also shows the need for achievement has a role in entrepreneurial intentions. Research by [55]-[57] states that the need for achievement has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial intentions. Dissenting opinions in the research of [58], [59] explain the need for achievement does not affect entrepreneurial intentions. The research result gap provides evidence that although people have the at the time, it does not affect the desire or intent to open a business or be self-employed. It is because Ngalang village people still lack knowledge and information about starting a business. People still feel comfortable by doing farming, breeding cattle, and cultivating lands. The potentials or talents possessed by the community that show the ability to excel have not been able to reach the stage of seeing entrepreneurial opportunities from natural potentials or environmental potentials, which are very much in Ngalang Village. The people still think that as long as their primary activity can provide sufficient for their

daily needs, they do not intend to run a business activity. McClelland [29] explained that someone with a high demand for achievement would prefer challenging activities requiring special skills and clear feedback to improve performance in business activity. Kasmir explained that cultivating entrepreneurial intentions takes a perfect, not half-hearted attitude and seriousness in running a business. Strengthened in the research of Ermawati *et al.* [54], the need for achievement influences entrepreneurial intentions through a perfect attitude (proper attitude).

The fourth hypothesis test shows a positive and very significant influence between entrepreneurial orientation and entrepreneurial intentions in society. This result is corroborated by Ibrahim and Lucky's research [17] which explains that entrepreneurial orientation has a positive and significant effect on the entrepreneurial intentions of Nigerian students in Malaysia. In their study, Kreiser *et al.* [60], also based on the theory put forward by Covin and Slevin [27], that the three dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation include innovation which can be defined as a willingness to support creativity and experimentation in creating and introducing business products. Someone with a high entrepreneurial orientation will be more open to new things to generate creative ideas [61]. The indicators in the model imply that dominant innovation reflects an entrepreneurial orientation. Covin and Slevin [27] explained that innovation is the core of a person to foster entrepreneurial intentions in him. The risk-taking aspect is the calculated risk concept, which has long been associated with entrepreneurship. The definition centers on an entrepreneur's willingness to engage in risk associated with the venture being estimated. The entrepreneur's attitude is boldly taking risks in uncertainty to achieve the planned business objectives, including seeking profits and developing the business [62]. Proactiveness (Proactive) is seen as an opportunity seeker, a forward-looking perspective characterized by new products and services ahead of the competition and acting to anticipate future demands [63]. These three elements are closely related to entrepreneurial intentions because the ability to innovate, take risks or risk management, seek opportunities, and compete will become the provision to increase their entrepreneurial intentions. Individuals with innovation, proactivity and the courage to take risks will derive the intention to open and run their businesses [60], [62].

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and discussion above, it can be concluded that the designed entrepreneurial intention model is fit between theoretical and empirical data in the field. The model is acceptable to explain the relationship between the influence of exogenous variables consisting of family support, need for achievement, and entrepreneurial orientation on entrepreneurial intentions in the people of Ngalang Village. The results of hypothesis testing show partially that family support and entrepreneurial orientation have a positive and very significant effect on entrepreneurial intentions. In contrast, the need for achievement does not affect people's entrepreneurial intentions at Ngalang Village. Further research can be suggested using attitude or entrepreneurial knowledge variables as mediator variables on entrepreneurial intentions. Knowledge of entrepreneurship for the residents of Ngalang Village means that there is still no self-motivation to cultivate the intention to become an entrepreneur.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Fatwa Tentama is an associate professor at the Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta. His scientific field is Industrial and Organizational Psychology with a focus on work attitudes and work behavior. The research theme focuses on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), employability, work readiness, entrepreneurship readiness, entrepreneurial intentions, contextual performance and others. He can be contacted at email: fatwa.tentama@psy.uad.ac.id.

Surahma Asti Mulasari is an associate professor at the Faculty of Public Health, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta. She has a focus on scientific fields, namely public health and environmental health. The research conducted is related to the theme of environmental quality analysis, environmental management policies and management, as well as appropriate technology in the environmental field. She can be contacted at email: surahma.mulasari@ikm.uad.ac.id.

Tri Wahyuni Sukesi is an associate professor at the Faculty of Public Health, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta. Tri Wahyuni Sukesi focuses on the scientific community of public health and environmental health. The current research is themed environmental analysis and sanitation, environmental control and environment-based disease control. She can be contacted at email: tri.sukesi@ikm.uad.ac.id.

Sulistyawati is an associate professor at the Faculty of Public Health, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta. Sulistyawati has a scientific focus, namely public health and epidemiology. Current research is related to health systems, disease epidemiology and geographic information systems for health. She can be contacted at email: sulistyawati.suyanto@ikm.uad.ac.id.

Subardjo is a professor at the Faculty of Law, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta. Subardjo has a focus on scientific fields, namely constitutional law and research methodology. The current research is related to research methodology, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), discipline, and constitutional law. He can be contacted at email: subardjo@law.uad.ac.id.